

DESIGNING NEEDS ANALYSIS QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ESP LEARNERS

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Annotation. This article explores the significance of needs analysis in ESP course development, discussing its methods, types and benefits in the teaching as well as learning process. Moreover, this research uses questionnaire and interview methods to analyze the example of need analysis questionnaire and its outcomes amid medical students and doctors with the new finding about how medicals interact with this method and their expectations as well as needs from today's modern English language learning program as one type of ESP learners

Key words. Needs analysis, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), course design, learner-centered approach, medical English, language proficiency, questionnaire, ESP learners, teaching methodology

To begin with, The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of higher education" radically changes the content of personnel training in accordance with the priority tasks of fundamental improvement of the higher education system, socio-economic development of the country [1] It is designed to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists in accordance with international standards. During the years of independence, a lot of work has been done to modernize the higher education system, introduce modern forms and technologies of vocational training and improve the skills of specialists, taking into account the real needs of the economy and social life [3:1]. In the field of English language teaching, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has become remarkably crucial due to the high demand for language competency customized to professional, academic, or occupational contexts. Unlike EAP courses (English for Academic Purposes), ESP programs aim to teach language skills for non-language oriented professionals directly related to their specific spheres such as medicine, law or business.

In the foundation of effective ESP courses lies well-organized documents complex in which needs analysis plays a vital for choosing appropriate methods and material for learners since it is the process of identifying what learners know and need to know, how they can learn the language from their preferences. According to Burksaitiene, "Needs analysis is the key to collect insider's view of the ESP situation and the views of chosen learners are of utmost importance" [1:330]. Now that needs analysis is goal-oriented, it makes teachers avoid delivering content which does not meet learners' needs and expectations. Saragih states that needs analysis is vitally important in designing teaching materials for English for Specific Purposes [2:59]. In that case, needs analysis aids identify the specific language tasks that learners face in their real-world tasks and this allow instructors to design lessons, course materials and techniques that reflect these tasks which contribute course's engagement and meaningfulness. Furthermore, by implementing needs analysis survey, the difference between learner's current language level and the proficiency they intend to reach for their professional or academic roles can be revealed. Another important point is the promotion of learner motivation with the instructors' attention and interest to the learners' requirements. When the learner realizes that the course addresses

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their goals and challenges, they are more likely to be encouraged to learning. As ESP learners have diverse learning styles based on their professions, positions, demands and interests, the teaching environment will be varied according to their learning styles. Needs analysis enables teachers to tailor the course content and approach, methods be accordingly fit learners study styles and skills. Consequently, a course built on true understanding of learner needs is more likely to achieve desired objectives as it focuses on practical applications and relevant skills. So, needs analysis is not only preliminary step of designing ESP course, it is key factor determining the courses effectiveness and success.

Based on the learners' specific language needs and professional purposes, needs analysis survey can be varied in several forms such as target situation analysis questionnaire, present situation analysis questionnaire, learning needs analysis, deficiency analysis and wants analysis questionnaire types. In order to reach high efficiency of this survey to organize ESP course, the instructor can mix the questions of different forms of questionnaires relying on the creativity and experience of the instructor.

In regard to conducting needs analysis for ESP lessons, teacher should carefully choose the appropriate methods that will help to collect reliable and relevant information. When a triangulated approach is used like combining at least two methods like written questionnaire+ observation+ interview, more complete and satisfied results can be achieved. Besides these, in organizing ESP courses focus groups, analysis of authentic materials and self-assessment tools methods are also utilized in different situations based on objective and subjective factors like preferences of teacher, aims of the course etc.

There are some tips for ESP teachers to design result-oriented and successful needs analysis questionnaire which do also help learners identify their real needs and aims to learn the target language. Any teacher who is considering to draft needs analysis questionnaire should focus on the following points. Firstly, in order to evoke the intention and encouragement, learners are be aware of the purpose of the needs analysis that they are conducting to and explain that their responses are crucial as a key for organizing learning and teaching process with polite and clear language. Secondly, security is an important factor that any learner may worry about the unfavorable impact on their study. That's why in questionnaire, learners are be informed in advance that their responses will be used merely to organize course and choose appropriate methods and materials. The format and style of the questions should be clear and polite with simple words considering they are non-specialized professionals of language. The questions should not be so long and complex requiring long and deep thinking which can be ruminating for responders.

Here is given a sample of needs analysis questionnaire for medical students to analyze in depth.

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ESP LEARNERS

The purpose of the questionnaire is to identify learners' needs and interests, so you are kindly requested to select any options which help to make your learning process to be both easier and more efficient.

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Personal Information

Name / Surname:	
Specialty:	
Age:	

1) Have you studied English before? (If yes, please write down your current level)

- Yes _____
 No
 other _____

2) Which skill would you like to improve?

- Speaking
 Reading
 Writing
 Listening
 other _____

3) What is the purpose of learning English?

- for work
 for travel
 for communication
 for IELTS / Multilevel certificate
 other _____

4) What kind of resources would you like to use during the classes?

- visual aids
 handouts
 textbook
 other _____

5) Do you work with digital tools?

- Yes
 No
 other _____

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- 6) You would prefer to work _____
- individually
 - in pairs
 - in groups
 - other _____
- 7) Which aspect of medicine would you like to be more focused on?
- medical consilium
 - terminology
 - diagnostic screening
 - medical procedures
 - diseases / symptoms
 - other _____
- 8) How long are you planning to learn English?
- 1-4 months
 - 5-8 months
 - 1 year
 - other _____
- 9) How often would you like to attend English classes per week?
- 2 days per week
 - 3 days per week
 - other _____
- 10) How many hours can you spare per lesson?
- up to 1 hour
 - up to 2 hours
 - other _____

This questionnaire covers all core areas of learner needs, including personal background, language proficiency and skills, learning goals, resource preferences and content relevance. Questionnaire is divided into two parts for personal and specific information beginning with informing the aim of the questionnaire for learners using kind and polite style to ask to response the given questions explaining beneficial sides for their study. The format of questionnaire is simple multiple-choices without a bulk of words and questions.

In personal information section, name and surname is given to identify the learner. Its is useful for organizing individual learner profile. Next question will be about their specialty to determine the learner's field in medicine. This question aids instructor customize vocabulary texts, and role plays relevant to their different specialties. After that, learner's age will be asked which influence learning style, digital tool familiarity and scheduling preferences. These three basic questions are enough for personal data and other unimportant information is not be needed for course organization.

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In the next part, learners will fulfill specific questions about language proficiency. To determine prior language learning experience and current level, responders are asked about background knowledge which is crucial for grouping them and designing level-appropriate materials. In order to identify priority skills, learners will choose the skill they would like to improve. This helps tailor lessons to focus on the most needed skills. Understanding learners' goals and requirements of learning the language supports personalized instruction. For instance, those studying for IELTS need exam strategies, while others who want to travel may need more communication tips or for other ones workplace needs. For designing learning materials and choosing visual aids, the recourses they would like to use during the classes will be asked to promote learner-centered teaching. It also represent whether learners prefer traditional or modern methods which guide the teacher to identify teaching approach and methodology. To evaluate digital literacy, it's essential to know whether learners work with digital tools like Zoom, Google, Docs or apps to help teacher to organize blended learning or online lessons to avoid the same teaching styles or be ready for different situations. Using technology in lessons encourage learners to use the target language for participating online conferences or applying articles for other countries which will be needed in their profession. Besides these, to understand learners' social learning preferences, their learning styles will be asked for class organization and engagement. Some learners may be more confident in pairs or groups, while others may prefer to work individually. So the teacher can design tasks and activities according to their preferences. To identify specific medical content needs, the aspect of medicine they want to be more focused on will be determined in order to select real-life case studies, vocabulary sets and scenarios directly aligned with learners' fields and interests. Since from the content of each lesson to simple details of exercises like example sentences will be around their sphere, their engaged aspects of medicine will be needed to collect authentic materials. The determination of the intended duration of study helps in planning course length, pacing and long-term goals. It also sets realistic expectations for language improvement over time. The syllabus of the course should be designed based on this time duration. In scheduling and deciding between intensive or extensive learning programs, time availability of learners' to attend classes per week would be given in questionnaire. The last question will be about the hours that they can spare per lesson. It assists design lesson content and activities accordingly considering their time availability. Now that time management is essential skill for any teacher as short sessions may require more focused tasks, while longer ones can include multiple skill areas, learners should manage all lessons and tasks, teacher must take into account the time commitment.

Conclusion. The analyzed needs analysis questionnaire demonstrates significant value in organizing a well-structured and learner-centered ESP course, particularly for medical professionals. Each questionnaire item contributes directly to tailoring a learner-centered ESP course that reflects the specific professional and linguistic needs of its participants. The questionnaire effectively gathers critical data that supports the development of a purposeful, targeted and professionally relevant ESP program. Each question serves as a map for teacher to organize successful course taking learners' needs and interests into consideration which leads the instructor to manage create the whole course materials complex based on learner' learning styles and requirements. By aligning language instruction with learners' specific needs and contexts, it enhances both the efficiency and impact of the learning process.

References

1. Burksaitiene & Tereseviciene. (2008). Integrating Alternative learning and assessment in a course of English for law students. Lithuania, Vytautas Magnus University. V 33, N 2
2. Saragih, E. (2014). Designing ESP Materials for Nursing Students based on Needs Analysis. International Journal of Linguistics, V6, N 4
3. Tajieva A., Babaniyazova N. Educational reforms in the republic of Uzbekistan in operation // Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2015. – T. 7. – №. 27. – C. 134-137.

